

Voltage Stability Enhancement Using Cat Swarm Optimization Algorithm

Authors : P. Suryakumari, Dr. P. Kantarao

Abstract : Optimal Power Flow (OPF) problem in electrical power system is considered as a static, non-linear, multi-objective or a single objective optimization problem. This paper presents an algorithm for solving the voltage stability objective reactive power dispatch problem in a power system .The proposed approach employs cat swarm optimization algorithm for optimal settings of RPD control variables.. Generator terminal voltages, reactive power generation of the capacitor banks and tap changing transformer setting are taken as the optimization variables. CSO algorithm is tested on standard IEEE 30 bus system and the results are compared with other methods to prove the effectiveness of the new algorithm. As a result, the proposed method is the best for solving optimal reactive power dispatch problem.

Keywords : RPD problem, voltage stability enhancement ,CSO algorithm.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014